

1 **Replication as salvation: the politics of open science and the recurring allure of**
2 **scientism in deep-time lithic studies**

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4 Shumon T. Hussain^{1,2,*}

5 ¹ Multidisciplinary Environmental Studies in the Humanities (MESH), Faculty of Arts and
6 Humanities, University of Cologne, Cologne, Germany

7 ² Department of Prehistoric Archaeology, Faculty of Arts and Humanities, University of
8 Cologne, Cologne, Germany

9 * Author for correspondence: s.t.hussain@uni-koeln.de

10 ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6215-393X>

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21 **Abstract**

22 There is a nascent body of literature in deep-time lithic studies that has declared replication
23 an aim of research, diagnosing the field to be deeply affected by the replication crisis, and
24 positioning reproducibility and replicability at the core of what science ought to be. The
25 paper examines this debate, its rhetorics, and its underlying normative and epistemological
26 commitments. I caution against the tendency to muster replication as a new-found yardstick
27 of scientificity, to conflate science with replication, and to overlook the broader knowledge-
28 making interests and goals of the field as a whole. I propose that current debates on
29 replication are premised on a specific vision of what science is, which not only appears to be
30 anachronistic but also threatens to promote tropes of scientism and to restrict the scope of
31 lithic inquiry, hence conflicting with values such as epistemic diversity and justice long
32 deemed central to scientific pursuits. I argue that overemphasizing the demands of replication
33 can therefore have deleterious consequences for lithic studies and that it can only be a token
34 of good scientific practice if mobilized in such a way that it actually supports, rather than
35 curtails, other key normative concerns and diverse knowledge-making projects within the
36 field. I contend that an object-oriented understanding of science is at the root of the problem
37 and that practitioners would be well-advised to invert the directionality of how openness is
38 implemented in lithic studies, putting much more weight on inclusivity than on strongly
39 context-dependent parameters such as transparency and quality.

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41 **Keywords:** Archaeological knowledge, lithic technology, replication crisis, epistemic justice,
42 critical pluralism, Open Science

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45 **Introduction**

46 There is a climate of mistrust engulfing the projects of science (Oreskes, 2021; Leonelli,
47 2023). Yet the sort of mistrust that matters here is not merely an issue of how a so-called
48 ‘public’ perceives and engages with time-honed scientific institutions as Bates (1997)
49 famously cautioned in his *Nature* editorial of 1997, but equally pertains to how practitioners
50 relate to *each other* within science and their specific disciplines or fields of research – who is
51 ultimately accepted as a fellow scientist, a peer, or a relevant interlocutor. The climate of
52 mistrust, in other words, has resulted in much *a priori* scepticism about other, non-shared
53 perspectives or broader research positionalities and – especially well-documented in the
54 history of archaeology (Sørensen, 2017) and its deep-time segments (Hussain, 2019, 2021) –
55 put a lot of strain on what can count as ‘science’ in the first place. I argue that the uncritical
56 acceptance of a widely proclaimed ‘replication crisis’ (Ioannidis, 2005; Baker, 2016) across
57 the sciences – notwithstanding notable objection and critique – is about to further fuel such
58 divisionary politics within archaeology, and notably in lithic studies. This is because many of
59 the emerging voices who emphatically push for the need to enhance replicability wittingly or
60 unwittingly yearn to advance a particular model of science. I here wish to draw attention to
61 some blind-spots of the associated replicability discourse, notably the i) commitment to a
62 largely outdated vision of what science is, ii) the related risk to plunge into self-defeating
63 postures of scientism, iii) and the dangers to invert the initial ambition to ‘open up’ scientific
64 inquiry by *de facto* neatly corralling it, thereby not only overlooking the implicit normativity
65 of current replicability conversations but also underestimating the potentially curtailing
66 effects of such politics on other values which are of critical importance to safeguard ‘good
67 science’ such as *epistemic diversity* and *justice* (Leonelli, 2023). I briefly examine these
68 issues in relation to recent concerns in deep-time lithic studies.

69 This paper therefore has several aims. While I squarely recognize the benefits of
70 engaging with issues of replicability in archaeology, I want to caution practitioners to not
71 blindly buy into all of the attendant rhetorics, and to carefully think about the relationship
72 between its core aspirations and the functioning and goals of the discipline. Such concerns
73 are currently hardly discussed in print, and I believe this must change. In a time of fierce
74 reactionary push-back, I also want to alert practitioners to not diminish, or even roll back, the
75 achievements of disciplinary traditions which at first glance seem less compatible with Open
76 Science (OS) and replicability projects as currently articulated in the literature. As such, it is
77 imperative to monitor the potential colonization and instrumentalization of the replication
78 crisis by efforts to revert the field back in the outdated image of a strictly ‘scientific’
79 archaeology as initially envisaged by archaeological processualists. Taking replicability
80 seriously, I maintain, must also mean to resist totalizing it as salvation.

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82 **Replication in deep-time lithic studies**

83 Lead voices of the CoMSAfrica project – bringing together diverse lithic scholars working on
84 the African Middle Stone Age in a notable attempt to develop a ‘unified comparative
85 approach and shared units of analysis’ – symptomatically concluded that ‘objectivity and
86 replicability are two fundamental requirements of science’ (Will *et al.*, 2019: 57), and as lithic
87 analysis – a core practice of deep-time archaeology (Hussain, 2019; Hussain and Soressi,
88 2021) – aspires to live up to such scientific standards, it must also commit itself to these
89 requirements. These proclamations rarely unpack what is understood as ‘replicability’ or
90 ‘objectivity’, of course, and their appeal to a monolithic and neatly integrated corpus of lithic
91 data and knowledge is not new; with a dose of parody, we can easily appreciate that the
92 history of lithic studies is in fact sprinkled with such efforts, a notable example being the

93 endeavours of Desmond J. Clark and his collaborators in the 1960s and 1970s. In a recent
94 study explicitly centring replicability, Pargeter and colleagues (2023: 164) similarly insist in a
95 firm tone that, in their view, to serve the comparative ambition of lithic research, individual
96 data points need to be ‘robust’, ‘repeatable’ and ‘comparable’ (measured against a common
97 standard). They are particularly concerned with ‘data congruence’ and explicitly make it a
98 primary goal of deep-time lithic studies to ‘achieve high consistency and low error rates when
99 recording and measuring attributes on lithic artefacts between observers’; they even assert
100 that ‘analytical standardization is undisputed’ – which is contentious – even though it remains
101 unclear whether they refer to pragmatic or epistemological callings. Being wary about, and
102 testing for, inter-observer variance or ‘error’ is indeed a long-standing preoccupation of what
103 I have previously called ‘analytic’ lithic research (Hussain, 2019), and it often goes hand in
104 hand with a forthright anxiety about what is purportedly ‘subjective’ in lithic observation –
105 stigmatized as ‘immersive’, ‘hyper-interpretive’ or as ‘palaeopsychology’. This strand of
106 lithic knowledge production commonly adopts what Leonelli (2023) has called an ‘object-
107 oriented’ mode of science, centring shared methods and protocols as well as the
108 interoperability and tradeability of lithic data, code and broader digital infrastructures, and it
109 draws on a well-trying tradition of discomfort vis-à-vis human cognitive capabilities, trusting
110 instead in what Lucas (2022) calls ‘machine epistemology’. Replicability is thus frequently
111 modelled in relation to the ideal of a *dehumanized* science – a science in which, at the
112 extreme, hardly any human import is required and/or hailed.

113 In deploying machine learning-based image classification techniques to sort through
114 lithic microdébitage, Eberl and colleagues (2023) for example aim to offer an ‘alternative’ to
115 ‘manual approaches that are prone to intra- and interobserver errors’, and Timbrell et al.
116 (2022: 209) are similarly concerned with testing, and ultimately minimizing, ‘inter-observer
117 error’ in metric and geometric morphometric (GMM) data recordings, and they, following

118 Marwick and colleagues (2017), explicitly situate their attempts within archaeology’s OS
119 initiative, which ‘advocates that data stewardship should be centred around researchers
120 collecting and sharing data on behalf of the scientific community’. In Leonelli’s (2023) terms,
121 the kind of openness these and other efforts have in mind is the *freedom to share*, the
122 scientific process is modelled as a directed, compositional assembly line – reminiscent of
123 capitalist market places and aspiring ideals of free trade policies – and the epistemic priority
124 is unmistakably placed on *sharing* and *quality* insurance, resulting in a particular ‘direction of
125 travel’ of core values underpinning OS implementations (**Fig. 1**). This tends to reduce
126 knowledge production to a mere question of correctly managing the right epistemic
127 resources, rendering the researcher in principle interchangeable and fostering a resource-
128 centric and extractivist political economy of science. Note that this dependence is not
129 inevitable and the relationship between OS and Open Society, although influential in the
130 development and legitimation of OS frameworks, is open to debate.¹ It is also worth
131 highlighting – especially given archaeology’s colonial binds – that this conception of
132 openness compels practitioners to ‘collate’, ‘farm’, ‘select’ and ‘refine’ their epistemic
133 resources (data, methods, protocols, etc.) – i.e., to ‘domesticate’ and ‘breed’ them, only to
134 later ‘harvest’ and bring them to effective use wherever needed. It is not simply a coincidence
135 here that Darwin’s evolution by natural selection was originally inspired by observations in
136 British sheep breeding, that scientific progress continues to be understood as a form of
137 evolution operating by similar mechanisms (Stewart and Plotkin, 2021), and that the resulting
138 vision of science forwards *control* as a key epistemic principle – a view of science now
139 increasingly critiqued (Staddon, 2018; Oreskes, 2021; Santo, 2024).

¹ This includes the question of what Open Society is or ought to be (and/or, relatedly, *which* Open Society to invoke as a benchmark).

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141 **Figure 1.** Traditional model of core values in OS implementation and their ‘direction of travel’

142 (redrawn from Leonelli, 2023: Fig. 1).

143 Trustworthiness, reproducibility and the robusticity of analytical systems gradually
144 moved to the centre of methodological debates in lithic studies, both with regard to artefact-
145 level analysis and higher-level lithic patterns and phenomena (Clark and Riel-Salvatore,
146 2006; Reynolds and Riede, 2019; Riede *et al.*, 2020; Barton and Clark, 2021). On the level of
147 individual artefacts, most studies have focused on trait-based and metric observations, with
148 the recent addition of probing into the capacity of 2D and 3D GMM methods to capture
149 similar patterns (e.g., Matzig, Hussain and Riede, 2021), while few studies systematically
150 examined the inter-observer consistency of specific methods, for instance Kot *et al.* (2025)
151 who tested diacritical analysis (scar-pattern analysis) by drawing on experimental lithic
152 artefacts with known knapping trajectories, showing that the relationship between the
153 reproducibility and reliability of results is often not straightforward. Reproducibility has also
154 explicitly been identified as a major weakness of large-scale classification systems, from
155 more traditional tool typologies to techno-complexes and cultural taxonomies (Riede, 2017;
156 Riede, Hoggard and Shennan, 2019; Wilkins, 2020; Araujo and Okumura, 2021; Gennai,
157 2021), even though methodical work on both fronts often yields mixed or even encouraging
158 results (Prentiss, 1998; Riede *et al.*, 2024). In these debates, it is increasingly important to
159 pay attention to the distinction between *reproducibility* and *replicability*, the former referring
160 to ‘to computational “artifacts” – things such as code, data, images, etc., created and used in
161 the process of generating archaeological results’ (Farahani, 2024) – and only the latter being

162 concerned with the recreation or reenactment of similar results, not least because what can
163 count as successful replication, including what is similar enough, is not always clear and
164 needs to be carefully discussed (Nosek *et al.*, 2022; Peels and Bouter, 2023).

165 In deep-time lithic studies, however, it is often simply assumed that the freedom to
166 share promoting reproducibility automatically increases the replicability of results as well;
167 even worse: that reproducibility, replicability, and the veracity of knowledge in this way
168 attained follow from, and safeguard, each other. They often do not (McElreath and Smaldino,
169 2015; Smaldino and McElreath, 2016), and it has been shown, for example, that low
170 replicability can in some cases enhance robust, efficient science (Lewandowsky and
171 Oberauer, 2020), in part also because what is replicated is often merely bias and entrenched
172 ways of doing things. A key problem, therefore, more generally, seems to be that the call for
173 replication in science is easily confused with *science being replication*, or at least that
174 scientificity can be guaranteed simply by committing to replicability in research design and
175 practice. This not only risks to elevate replicability to an end in itself, and thus to lose sight of
176 the diverse epistemic interests, goals, and knowledge ambitions that long drive the field
177 (Vaesen and Hussain, 2025), it also severely underestimates the imbalance of epistemic risk
178 and epistemic gain characterizing lithic inquiry as a critical and open-ended endeavour. The
179 most reproducible observations and most replicable findings may be precisely those with a
180 low sealing of epistemic reach and reduced potential of insight, so that insisting on
181 replicability as a new ‘gold standard’ of lithic inquiry unnecessarily limits what can be
182 credibly said and known about the lithic archaeological record. This is ultimately what is put
183 at stake when leaning too strongly into an ‘object-oriented’ understanding of science and how
184 it advances, and I argue that this is particularly so in lithic analysis.

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186 **Replication and scientificity: epistemological pluralism and the perils of scientism**

187 In a paper entitled ‘Is archaeology a science?’, Ben Marwick (2025), following on similar
188 statements in the 40th anniversary editorial of the Journal of Archaeological Science
189 (Torrence, Martínón-Torres and Rehren, 2015), explicitly and unmistakably links the
190 question of reproducibility to ‘archaeology’s status as a science’. In support of his arguments,
191 Marwick (2025) mobilizes bibliometric data from the same journal as evidence of
192 archaeology’s place in the sciences (rather than the humanities), especially the social sciences
193 (see also Smith *et al.*, 2012 for other arguments on this matter). He invokes reproducibility as
194 a ‘crucial factor that separates scientific practice from non-science’ and quotes a US National
195 Science Foundation report from 2015 asserting that ‘reproducibility is a minimal necessary
196 condition for a finding to be believable and informative’.² He not only assumes that
197 consensus-making is generally promoted by reproducibility – scientific consensus involves
198 complex forms of negotiation and how to establish it can thus vary dramatically across and
199 within fields – he also conjures it as a ‘cornerstone of rigorous science’ and as an at least
200 indirect measure of the performance of a scientific community. Marwick (2017) has
201 previously suggested that among the primary benefits of implementing routines of
202 reproducibility within archaeology is increased community *impact*, measured simply by the
203 number of citations received by OS-promoting papers. I am concerned about such framings
204 not just because they tacitly position reproducibility as an unassailable proxy for the
205 relevance of archaeological research (and potentially also its significance), they risk to
206 confuse the ‘empirical’ with the ‘desirable’, and they inscribe into the type of resource-centric
207 political economy of science described above, but also because they normalize trading and re-
208 using these resources as aspirational end itself and tend to galvanize an understanding of

² This strong wording stands in notable tension with Marwick’s (2025) discussion of qualitative archaeological research and sciences-humanities relationships in a separate subsection at the end of the paper where the tone is substantially lowered and the position somewhat defused.

209 archaeological science as largely unified – based on a circumscribed set of shared resources –
210 and as committed to a settled, uncontentious *philosophy of science*. I suggest that both
211 assumptions are misleading but consequential for the politics of replication.

212 As Marwick (2025) himself admits, archaeology is far from a homogeneous
213 enterprise, different archaeologists participate in, and variously contribute to, different
214 knowledge-making projects and pursue different research interests, objectives and even onto-
215 epistemological commitments (e.g., Corbey, 2005; Lucas, 2017), and deep-time lithic studies
216 is not exempt from this basic condition of research (Hussain, 2019, 2021, in press). As I have
217 shown elsewhere, already in the Western European arena of lithic inquiry this diversity of
218 pursuits turns out to be a fundamental source for the creativity, proficiency, and versatility of
219 research – it is enabling rather than curtailing – and it pertains not merely to how findings are
220 evaluated and interpreted but is instead linked to the recognition and valorisation of *different*
221 *sets* of basic epistemic resources, including the kind of lithic observations that matter and
222 how these are translated into, and stylized as, ‘data’ (Hussain, 2019). Moreover, different
223 configurations of such resources, when interrogated in their attendant cognitive systems of
224 engaging with and theorizing lithic technology, are capable of delivering different sorts of
225 insights, support different kinds of interpretations about the past, and are generally able to
226 advance different facets of disciplinary knowledge. The lithic data that is most integral to
227 these different ways of doing lithic analysis may in fact be varyingly receptive to replication
228 as construed through the freedom to share lens – a blind-spot of the debate.

229 For example, state-of-the-art *chaîne opératoire* research in the French tradition
230 commonly relies on higher-level observations not reducible to the morphological, trait-based
231 and techno-typological data currently at the heart of replicability discussions (cf. esp. Will *et*
232 *al.*, 2019; Pargeter *et al.*, 2023), instead focusing on whole-artefact interrelations including
233 their morphotechnical consequences on each other as well as the role and place of individual

234 artefacts, or groups of functionally analogous artefacts, within larger operational sequences
235 (Hussain, 2019). The point is not that inferences here are in principle incompatible with
236 reproducibility demands but that their *standards* may widely differ. What is in need of being
237 traded and standardized may then be descriptions of technical relationships of concern,
238 systems of such relationships, and what particular lithic operational sequences enable and
239 close-off as they unfold; in many cases, the goal is not to reliably record any given, isolated
240 lithic artefact but to determine which artefacts results from, and thus participate in, which
241 ways of reducing (which) larger original volumes. Replication may then not hinge so much
242 on artefact-level data, but on effective and traceable visual demonstration that grouping lithic
243 artefacts in particular ways and linking them to other groups or kinds of artefacts in specific
244 spatial (related to core reduction surfaces) and temporal arrangements (along a reduction
245 continuum or broader stages thereof) helps to make sense, and thereby resolve, the
246 encountered total lithic phenotypic variability. Importantly, promoting *replication* in such
247 cases cannot be achieved simply by invoking the lithic data Pargeter and colleagues (2023)
248 are concerned with, for example, but relies on the documentation of all artefacts grouped
249 together (as irreducible whole-artefacts), or selected prototypical instances thereof, and an
250 argument-driven description of the epistemic efficacy of such grouping(s) – a fundamental
251 reason why much of the relevant data may indeed be *visual* and *associative* (cf. Hussain,
252 2021) and in need of complementary *natural language explanations*. Rigorous *chaîne*
253 *opératoire* research of this kind cannot be replaced by other ways of analysis, and the
254 demands of its own standards of scientific rigor showcase that what can count as ‘rigorous’
255 depends on the research context and accepted practices, and thus cannot be subsumed under
256 the hegemonic grip of a monolithic understanding of rigor, especially if the very generativity
257 of the target set of practices and resources is thereby undermined.

258 State-of-the-art *chaîne opératoire* research often also exhibits a nexus of research
259 interests and goals not necessarily shared with other modes of lithic analysis and the
260 knowledge-making project tends to revolve around the identification, description,
261 interpretation and theorization of varying *ways of working* lithic raw materials – captured in
262 higher-level knapping modalities and methods or systems/patterns of débitage, façonnage,
263 and tool-making/use (and their associated operational schemes). Not only tend individual
264 artefact-level observations that score high on typical inter-analyst reproducibility scores – for
265 example artefact weight in Pargeter et al.’s (2023) study – to be relatively uninformative in
266 the context of such knowledge-making projects (cf. Vaesen and Hussain, 2025), framing
267 reproducibility in these terms misses the whole point of what *chaîne opératoire* analysis *does*
268 (and therefore enables in terms of knowledge production): it offers an account of how the
269 encountered lithic artefacts have co-constituted each other’s properties in a shared context of
270 lithic production; or, in other words, it seeks to provide an empirical characterization of the
271 *technological formation* of the target artefact assemblage(s). The inherent complexity of such
272 analysis is not the primary problem here – in computational applications, too, analytical
273 complexity is growing and often negatively linked to reproducibility success, for example
274 because of deep and nested dependency chains (Marwick, 2025). It would also be naïve to
275 assume that simpler and more elaborate or presuppositional analyses come with only minor
276 or neglectable differences in knowledge potential, and we thus need to make sure that in
277 practice reproducibility standards are not misused to discriminate between the two, notably if
278 the logics of research differ, so that what needs to be made transparent, verifiable, and
279 trackable and what kind of knowledge claims should be replicated also differs.

280 There is a more general point to be made here that reproducibility and replicability are
281 often premised on a broader, shared tradition of research, and that they frequently fail
282 precisely because of incommensurable cognitive frameworks of inquiry. We often cannot

283 faithfully reproduce the observations and the results of other studies if we do not know (or are
284 not trained in) how to observe and analyze the artefacts the way they do, and if the associated
285 normative (and often non-articulated) standards of research markedly collide. As I have
286 previously argued, much of the confusion on Levallois (e.g., Chazan, 1997; Sandgathe, 2004;
287 Bar-Yosef and Van Peer, 2009) boils down to this problem, and in reality reflects a struggle
288 to negotiate epistemic diversity while frantically clinging to unity of research aspirations, often
289 mixing superiority assumptions with ignorance (Hussain, 2019). If we are astutely aware of
290 these pitfalls, I believe it is reasonable to conclude that Levallois and other major patterned
291 ways of arranging and exploiting lithic raw materials such as Quina and Discoid have been,
292 as a matter of fact, well-replicated across a range of sites, periods, research contexts and
293 generation of researchers since at least the early 2000s. This does not mean, of course, that
294 these categories are not open to revision or that they represent irrevocable ‘truths’ (whatever
295 this would mean). To the contrary, the delineation between some of these categories is not
296 always clear (but the same is true for some biological species for instance) and Éric Boëda
297 (2013), one of the central figures in the initial description of these ways of stone working, has
298 recently presented a radical overhaul of relevant higher-level categories, focalising other
299 processes in lithic evolution and other observations in the artefactual material (see Boëda and
300 Chazan, 2023 for the recent English translation of this work). To incentivize such creative
301 work seeking to re-map higher-level patterns of lithic technological variability in relation to
302 novel research questions, hypotheses, and bodies of theory, it is important to not establish
303 prescriptive regimes of what can count as relevant and reliable data before such spaces have
304 even been properly explored, time-proofed, and critically assessed.

305 Indeed, my diagnosis of the French tradition in lithic technological analysis is that
306 part of its productivity and distinct community performance derives from its capacity for
307 devising ever-new *ways of seeing* (that is, observing and describing) lithics. It is an explicit

308 goal, for example, to detect unrecognised patterns and systems of lithic reduction including
309 their diverse behavioural affordances and repercussions – just think of newer discoveries such
310 as the existence of diverse approaches of bladelet or micro-point production before the fully
311 developed Upper Palaeolithic (e.g., Boëda and Bonilauri, 2006; Faivre, 2012; Zwyns *et al.*,
312 2012; Boëda *et al.*, 2015; Carmignani *et al.*, 2024) or regarding the nature of bipolar lithic
313 technology (Delpiano *et al.*, 2024). This research is discovery-driven precisely when it comes
314 to *observational realities* and it therefore relies on its ability to experiment with, and
315 continuously probe into, new ways of looking at lithic artefacts. This mode of research is in
316 clear practical tension with research that is self-proclaimed ‘data-driven’ because the latter
317 tends to overdetermine, and thereby formalize, how to datafy lithic artefacts, and in this way
318 promotes a standard gaze of lithic analysis, which struggles to relax, or even escape, its own
319 observational logic, let alone to recognize such effects. Since I argue that exploring and
320 tinkering with the full extent of the lithic observational space available to archaeologists,
321 including the encouragement of relevant conditions of novel observation, should be
322 recognized as a shared interest and broader objective of the field, data themselves need to be
323 kept open for revision and in need of constant re-assessment rather than posited as fixed
324 parameters of inquiry; they should accordingly not be closed off as ‘naturalized’ resources to
325 be merely traded and re-used. There are also other epistemological arguments for why lithic
326 data itself should be re-theorized and re-imagined in lithic practice; for example because
327 different scales of observation with their attendant levels of organization and emergent
328 phenomena likely require scale-commensurate observations to be adequately described and
329 understood (currently a hardly noticed issue in lithic studies: cf. Hussain, 2024). All of this
330 points to the dangers of curtailing what can count as ‘good practice’ or even ‘scientific’ under
331 the banner of at first sight unassailable concerns of reproducibility and replicability. We need
332 to keep a firm eye on the diverse epistemological interests and goals of the field and make

333 sure that competences to re-draw the boundaries of knowledge are cultivated rather than cut
334 back – and the rhetorics of replication are clearly not neutral in this.

335 This brings me directly to the issue of scientificity, what can count as ‘science’ and
336 how to encourage ‘good practice’ therein. Before anything else, it cannot be underscored
337 enough that these questions depend in large part, on the one hand, on the *philosophy of*
338 *science* we adopt and, on the other, and relatedly, on the kind of *virtue epistemology* we
339 endorse. Crucially, these issues are part of ongoing debates in a range of disciplines, and it
340 would be naïve to consider them settled in any way. To suggest that they are, and then heavily
341 leaning into this idea, was the fallacy committed by New Archaeologists and early
342 processualists such as Lewis Binford ([1989] 2016), who simply naturalized an influential
343 positivist strand of philosophy of science of their time as the singular road to securing
344 scientificity (cf. e.g., Earle *et al.*, 1987; Trigger, 2006). Hempel’s deductive-nomological
345 proposal of science has, for example, now been rejected as a universal model or benchmark
346 for the scientific endeavour as a whole, and even though it retains its importance for some
347 specific knowledge-making projects, in recent years a broad consensus has emerged that *in*
348 *actual practice* (that is, empirically), science is characterized, and typically thrives by, its
349 operational and epistemological *diversity* (e.g., Kellert, Longino and Waters, 2006; Chang,
350 2012; Ludwig and Ruphy, 2021; Cartwright *et al.*, 2022; Massimi, 2022), and that there is no
351 ‘unified’ science in the way even prominent 20th century theorists of science imagined (cf.
352 esp. Dupré, 1993; Hacking, 1996). Importantly, different sciences as well as sub-disciplinary
353 and transdisciplinary communities of research practice – and this includes the humanities –
354 have elaborated their own standards of scientificity, often based on unequal epistemological
355 and normative commitments. This should not be surprising, as from a metascientific
356 standpoint it invalidates the proposal of radical constructivism; instead, different knowledge
357 ventures respond to their particular objects of study in object-specific ways, delineating

358 relevant interests, problems, and questions (Leonelli, 2023). Such diversity is thus generally
359 deemed productive, generative, and necessary (see already Pepper, 1972), and it compels us
360 to accept *scientific pluralism* both as a reality and as desirable.

361 These developments have led to a momentous re-thinking of what science is and what
362 sets it apart from other human enterprises. Part of this ongoing conversation is also the
363 increasing realization that it is counterproductive – and ultimately self-defeating – to over-
364 strangulate, and thereby overburden, what can count as ‘scientific’ and what not (the
365 purported ‘non-scientific’), also because there is broad agreement that qualities such as
366 openness (as open-endedness and inclusivity), non-dogmatism, and self-revisionary ambition
367 are key to understanding the specificities of science, qualities which inevitably lead to an
368 ongoing expansion of the boundaries of science including its very definition. What science is
369 and what is accepted as scientific practice (and in what specific research context) is therefore
370 subject to constant assessment and re-evaluation itself – a reason why the original
371 ‘demarcation problem of science’ as forwarded by what is now often referred to as the
372 ‘normative project’ in the philosophy of science (cf. Dupré, 1993; in contrast to an
373 ‘anthropological’ or ‘praxis-oriented’ understanding of science: see e.g., Latour and Woolgar,
374 1986; Galison, 1997; Soler *et al.*, 2014) should be approached with due caution. In addition
375 to the charge of simply implanting a normative ideal as ‘normal science’ (sensu Kuhn, [1962]
376 2020) and *prescribing* science to follow this ideal rather than allowing it to unclasp and
377 evolve its own epistemological geography, strong notions of scientificity in the normative
378 tradition have been criticized as unrealistically idealistic, intellectualistic, and ahistorical
379 (e.g., Galison and Stump, 1996; Daston and Galison, 2010), as based on the prejudice and
380 stereotype of purported model disciplines such as physics and biology, and, more recently, as
381 Eurocentric as well as androcentric (cf. e.g., Haraway, 1991; Harding, 1991).

382 Recent investigations and debates in metascience – the science of science – have
383 thereby re-directed the attention from narrow conceptions of ‘objectivity’ (Daston and
384 Galison, 2010; Wylie, 2015) and the rhetorics of ‘The Scientific Method’ (Haufe, 2023;
385 Frank, Gleiser and Thompson, 2024) to how scientists actually *observe* phenomena and attain
386 knowledge about them in complex, real-world scenarios (Daston and Lunbeck, 2011). Such
387 rethinking of the foundations of science also brought to the fore that science can only be
388 properly characterized and understood if its *human-specific* properties are taken more
389 seriously (e.g., Massimi, 2022; Haufe, 2023; Leonelli, 2023). Scientific knowledge is pursued
390 in organized and structured *communities* of research with evolved mechanisms of self-
391 monitoring, self-critique, and self-revision (including but not limited to practices such as data
392 sharing and professional peer review: see esp. Oreskes, 2021 for the instructive example of
393 climate science) as well as patterns of cognitive labour division (Kitcher, 1990), for example
394 tied to specialization and epistemic task or remit. On a broad scale at least, such cognitive
395 division of scientific labour within disciplines or larger research programmes often comes
396 with different epistemological and normative commitments as those enable practitioners to
397 interact with the world in different ways, distinctively see and think about the world, and thus
398 attain original insights and understandings about it.

399 It is important to remember that replication has to be discussed in relation to this basic
400 situation and it must be harnessed to support the respective knowledge-making ventures, not
401 to override them and imposing new regimes of demands in the hope to homogenize them
402 because the unity of science is still the primary stereotype of scientificity in archaeology. This
403 may also mean, and therefore requires careful interrogation, that replication has to play a
404 different role in different lithic knowledge-making projects or research traditions, and we thus
405 need to be careful to properly translate its callings to their specific research logics. We
406 cannot, in other words, adopt an intuitive understanding of reproducibility and replicability,

407 which is, in reality, similarly fed by some underlying concept(s) of scientificity, and simply
408 assume its unwavering usefulness across all contexts of lithic knowledge-making. Instead, I
409 suggest we must be cognizant about the specificity of our time-honed ways of studying lithic
410 technology and muster replication *in their service*. Otherwise, we risk to severely shackle,
411 and hence curb, epistemic diversity, to unnecessarily put a strain on, or even marginalise,
412 some of these approaches, and to misidentify a *particular* interpretation of replication with
413 what the science of lithic studies purportedly *is* and *ought to be*. Not only because this
414 implicit positionality of replication debates is often overlooked, it seems imperative to make
415 sure that reproducibility and replicability are treated and discussed as *means*, and never as
416 self-sufficient ends, of the multi-stranded quest for lithic knowledge.

417 Acute attentiveness to the implicit metaphysical and normative commitments and
418 claims galvanized by particular rhetorics of replication is also pivotal because – as scholars
419 such as Susan Haack (2007) have long pointed out – the community-driven, open, non-
420 dogmatic, and self-correcting world engagement science emphatically stands for is not only
421 threatened from the outside – for example by growing anti-science sentiments – but also, and
422 at least equally forcefully, from within. This can take many forms and generally happens
423 when practitioners and the projects they promote undermine the conditions of diversity,
424 openness, and critical reflexivity – with attention recently paid especially to what has been
425 called ‘Science Triumphalism’ (Frank, Gleiser and Thompson, 2024) and ‘Scientism’ (Haack,
426 2012; Robinson and Williams, 2014; Stenmark, 2017). Science triumphalism has been
427 identified as an important source of the deepening planetary polycrisis, characterized
428 primarily by an pronounced overconfidence in the power of science, especially by virtue of
429 The Scientific Method, to answer all questions and solve all problems, the colonization and
430 marginalization of other fields and ways of knowing, and thus the overextension of its reach
431 and scope, while downplaying uncertainty and unpredictability, and denying, or ignoring, the

432 limits of scientific knowledge (Frank, Gleiser and Thompson, 2024). Scientism is a related
433 stance within science coming in many variants but generally positing that science not only is
434 the singular valid knowledge authority there is, science also, by virtue of its superior access
435 to reality, has revised, and thereby settled, the questions brought up by traditional
436 metaphysics, now supplying a ‘scientific metaphysics’. It tends to ally itself with one-world
437 ontologies (monism), recognizes only its own distinct form of rationality, and accuses other
438 ways of engaging with the world as ‘confused’, ‘biased’, and/or ‘misguided’.

439 The original project of rendering archaeology a ‘more scientific’ discipline as
440 championed by various processualists clearly had scientism-leanings, and some of these
441 tendencies still echo in recent pledges to the singular capacity of biomolecular and
442 palaeogenetic research to finally resolve long-standing archaeological questions (Kristiansen,
443 2014, 2017; see also Ribeiro, 2019 for a critique) and hold a traditionally strong foothold in
444 deep-time archaeologies, catalyzed by their often strong, openly confrontational and
445 commonly reductive, commitment to what is frequently seen as unimpeachable evolutionary
446 theory by those advocating for it (e.g., Clark, 2003; thereby ignoring, inter alia, that a major
447 transformation of evolutionary thinking is currently underway even in biology and that such
448 thinking is much less homogeneous and integrated than a stereotypical gaze may initially
449 suggest). Just as Lucas (2022) has rightly warned about the perils of using the rise of
450 computational, digital, and Big Data approaches and their commitment to ‘machine
451 epistemology’ as a pretext to, through the backdoor, finally fulfil some of the unmet
452 ambitions of processualism, lithic practitioners need to be equally cautious to not misuse the
453 replication crisis as a pretext to work towards the same tacit goals – i.e., to render lithic
454 studies ‘more scientific’, as if the field would not be scientific enough and we could
455 reasonably evaluate this from a distance. In particular in relation to issues of reproducibility
456 and replicability, as I have tried to show, the temptation is immense to evoke replication as a

457 yardstick of scientificity, to discriminate against other knowledge-making projects that
458 allegedly do not live up to its standards, and in often-exclusionary rhetorics link the fate of
459 the field to its capacity to develop a one-sided economy of replication, uncritically buying
460 into a particular vision of science and what putatively matters most in lithic studies.

461 I therefore argue that lithic scholarship is well-advised to closely monitor its
462 commitment to OS imperatives and to continuously re-evaluate their relationships to, and
463 implications for, particular ecosystems of scientific practice. Care needs to be exercised in
464 how reproducibility and replicability are defined, advertised, and framed, and whom such
465 framings serve, for what purpose, and why. Following other voices who have pointed out and
466 explored these issues much more comprehensively (Leonelli, 2023), we need to be keenly
467 aware that even good intentions can have (unwanted) deleterious effects and that lithic
468 scholars therefore need to be vigilant to not blindly lead the way towards implementation of
469 normative guidelines of purportedly ‘good practice’ in lithic studies which actually result in
470 the curtailing of epistemic diversity, worsen epistemic justice, and ultimately only benefit the
471 profusion of uninformative, unreliable, or even unethical lithic knowledge. Marwick (2025)
472 rightly points out that ‘gatekeeping’ positionalities among archaeologists too often prevent
473 the computational turn to be completed by OS practices and attitudes, but it is also important
474 to prevent the naturalization of a narrow understanding of these practices predicated on an
475 overly prescriptive concept of science, which in itself can easily promote yet another
476 gatekeeping regime, unjustly taxing those who do not (fully) subscribe to it – a reason why
477 the implicit normativity of research needs to be addressed proactively and heads-on, and why
478 ethical and epistemological concerns are difficult to separate (e.g., Pickering, 1995; Schurz
479 and Carrier, 2013; Longino, 2020; Leonelli, 2023). I will thus briefly draw attention to some
480 relevant normative concerns, before finally concluding my analysis.

481

482 **What is ‘good science’? A plea for humility and epistemic justice in lithic studies**

483 Rethinking the conditions of scientificity, and parallel efforts to move from ‘object-oriented’
484 to ‘process-oriented’ epistemologies of science (Leonelli, 2023), have made it sufficiently
485 clear that value assessments and judgements are at the core of science, and they, contra
486 popular beliefs, can and should not be purged from scientific practice (as values incite action
487 and actions forward values). Longino (2020) for example argues that the ‘objectivity’ of
488 science does not pertain to the absence of values as often assumed, but has to do with the
489 ability of socially organized communities of researchers to promote critical scrutiny,
490 collaboration, fairness, and inclusivity. Objectivity here is grounded not in the freedom to
491 share set-in-stone epistemic resources, but in the freedom to develop problem-specific
492 standards of inquiry and to contiguously monitor and revise or diversify those, often requiring
493 scholars to handle a multiplicity of epistemic resources with their own specific (but at the
494 same time evolving) standards of evaluation, critique, and knowledge corroboration. Looking
495 at science as a whole (and not only at specific disciplinary, sub-disciplinary, or
496 transdisciplinary ventures), objectivity can then be located in the capacity of a population of
497 heterogeneous researchers to compare, contrast, and learn from the takes and gains of divers,
498 situated modes of inquiry (Haraway, 1988) – objectivity in this view rests on the recognition
499 of perspectival partiality and the ongoing struggle to combat all forms of dogma (including
500 those reflected in the absolutizing gestures of academic scientism). As Oreskes argues in *Why*
501 *trust science?* (2021) – and I can only second this sentiment – we must resist the simplistic
502 diagnosis that the climate of distrust vis-à-vis a range of scientific findings and their possible
503 implications for action and thought has primarily to do with a *de facto* ‘degeneration’ of
504 scientific rationality, scrutiny, and rigor – and hence with the erosion of what science ought to
505 be; this is precisely the reading of the current situation amplifying the temptations of
506 scientism and positioning some of its claims as manifest remedies. Instead, we need to take

507 the above-summarised insights about the scientific process on board, and work on the
508 community-level processes of knowledge production, critique, corroboration that we valorise
509 because they make science an open, inclusive, and self-revisionary enterprise, guided not by
510 transcendental authority but collaborative scrutiny. To promote trust, it is therefore ill-advised
511 to insist on the superiority and prerogative of scientific knowledge, and we should rather
512 foreground its fallibility, partiality, and its institutionalized, ongoing overhaul.

513 This can, and often should, include various measures to enhance reproducibility and
514 replicability within different communities of research practice (such as in lithic studies), but it
515 also requires attention to the normative architecture of what we determine to be the
516 conditions of ‘good science’ (these are also always provisional, of course, in need of critical
517 interrogation, discussion, and constant re-evaluation). Drawing on long-standing and more
518 recent discussions in the philosophy of science and the ethics of the scientific conduct,
519 including but not limited to what is sometimes referred to as the field of *virtue epistemology*,
520 I want to highlight a few key coordinates of normative concern that have emerged from these
521 conversations and support the kind of scientificity defended here. These are *epistemic*
522 *humility, courage, justice* and the principle of *epistemic non-violence*, and they complement
523 the cherishing of *epistemic diversity* resulting from the recognition of the many benefits of
524 honing scientific pluralism (cf. Leonelli, 2023; see above).

525 Epistemic humility entails the awareness and open acknowledgement of the limits,
526 partialities, and blinds of one’s knowledge, understanding and intellectual capacities,
527 encompassing the admission that our views may be incomplete, biased, or outrightly flawed
528 and the openness to constantly check-in with new evidence, arguments and theoretical
529 insights to revise and adjust these views (e.g., Harding, 1991; Oreskes, 2021). It also involves
530 an attitude that casts participation in science as a journey of life-long learning and
531 development, that it is okay to not have all the answers (and to never attain them), and the

532 willingness to calibrate and review insights also in light of diverse other voices as well as to
533 take critical account of the related, sociocultural dimensions of public, and even global,
534 concern. Because such humility can be greatly encouraged by, and often benefits from,
535 practices of self-distancing and reflexivity, honesty and prudence in the face of one's own
536 knowledge situatedness – that we cannot escape the 'view from somewhere' and that it would
537 be hubris to claim otherwise – emerge as an important normative commitment of good
538 scientific practice. To value rather than talk down other knowledge-making positionalities is a
539 central pillar of lived epistemic humility. This is not merely an ethical issue as we simply
540 cannot know what other perspectives enable us to see, think about, and do with the world –
541 including what they perhaps allow us to better understand or to initially learn about this world
542 – and their epistemological utility should therefore constantly be probed, tested, and refined
543 (see esp. Pepper, 1972), thereby contributing to 'better science' overall. Building on Pepper
544 (1972) and drawing on Stroud (2015), I have previously termed this 'critical practice' and
545 identified it as a notable condition of knowledge advancement in lithic studies across varied
546 research traditions and unequal epistemological standpoints (Hussain, 2019). Epistemic
547 humility so understood generally promotes acute concerns about the restraints of one's own
548 epistemic gaze – what one regards as 'normal' science – including, for example, the in this
549 way possibly fostered 'coloniality of knowledge' (see e.g., Tuck and Yang, 2012; Hoagland,
550 2020; Shepherd, 2020) and its diverse imports and consequences.

551 Epistemic justice was vigorously brought to the attention of researchers and theorists
552 of science by Miranda Fricker's influential book *Epistemic Injustice: Power and the Ethics of*
553 *Knowing* (2007), and it has recently also become a notable concern within broader
554 discussions of OS implementation (Leonelli, 2023). Epistemic justice refers to 'wrong done
555 to someone specifically in their capacity as knower' (Fricker, 2007). In the case of lithic
556 studies, this may cover for example the exclusion of Indigenous voices, experiences, and

557 knowledge regimes in relation on stone artefact production and use (cf. González-Ruibal,
558 Hernando and Politis, 2011; Weedman Arthur, 2017) within broader lithic discourse; it can
559 also include practices of under-citation or the non-citation of generally relevant but
560 differently positioned work on topics of concern or within a shared research context, as well
561 as to ignore, understate, or grossly misrepresent the contribution of others due to stereotype –
562 what Fricker (2007) originally identified as ‘testimonial’ injustice. Massimi (2022) invokes
563 the notion of ‘epistemic severing’ to describe how prejudice can prevent careful consideration
564 of the targeted expertise even as an admissible source of insight, for instance because a lithic
565 researcher is surmised to merely advance a research project or tradition judged as ‘misguided’
566 or deeply ‘subjective’, or as ‘unscientific’ altogether – thus closing the circle and elucidating
567 how the politics of scientificity can weigh heavily on issues of epistemic justice and why
568 overstating one’s own scientific positionality is also a justice concern. Questions of
569 testimonial justice can easily turn into issues of ‘hermeneutical justice’ (Fricker, 2007),
570 especially when such negative stereotyping is generalized across a whole group of scholars,
571 and when entire ways of thinking and knowing which conflict with, or deviate from, one’s
572 own – notably other time-honed or emerging traditions of research – are perceived and
573 discredited as ‘unintelligible’ and/or ‘confused’ (cf. Leonelli, 2023: 37). Such issues of
574 hermeneutical justice can be varyingly configured and play out in diverse ways, but they are
575 of particular concern when this injustice is committed by the currently dominant and most
576 influential modes of doing research. This is why, in deep-time lithic studies, I would argue
577 that the marginalisation of certain forms of *chaîne opératoire* research strongly qualifies as
578 hermeneutical injustice and it can be traced by what I have described as ‘signature critique’,
579 which, although delineating failure to meaningfully engage with the other, shapes the
580 perception and recognition of such epistemic otherness (Hussain, 2019) – a reason why the
581 plural condition of lithic research ultimately tables demands of justice, demands that also

582 apply to OS practices and should therefore ground debates on replication, too. Another
583 general example is the in the social and natural sciences widespread view that qualitative or
584 mixed-methods researchers are ‘second-class scientists’ (Leonelli, 2023: 39), a perception
585 fuelled by problematic assumptions that hermeneutically unjustly discriminate against the
586 ‘hard-won, sophisticated methodological expertise cultivated within those fields’. The same
587 is true for self-assured qualitative-interpretive lithic technological research.

588 Justice concerns even apply to the politics of ‘access’ within OS initiatives. This is
589 because in some cases, unconditional open access policies, especially when coupled to
590 powerful reward systems, can exacerbate research inequalities as reproducible data and
591 replication studies can quicker and more effectively be generated by those with more
592 resources and more conducive infrastructures (Leonelli, 2023). The freedom to share can then
593 create the illusion of inclusivity and research participation, when in reality the fruits of such
594 data sharing are mainly harvested by those at the top of the data chain, typically powerful
595 players at well-funded research institutions in the Global North. The rhetorics of replication
596 can feed these dynamics and greatly amplify them, especially if the standards of what can
597 count as reproducible and replicable remains effectively withdrawn from scrutiny. I see some
598 signs of this in the nascent literature on replication in deep-time lithic studies and I urge lithic
599 practitioners and other archaeologists alike to remain vigilant in the face of such
600 developments, and to carefully interrogate and discuss them. Addressing the replication crisis
601 in lithic studies and elsewhere simply cannot come at the costs of furthering of what has been
602 called ‘epistemic imperialism’ (e.g., Benhabib, 2002; Ngugi wa Thiong’o, 2011; Santos,
603 2016), and it must admit to the principle of reducing epistemic harm and strive to prune
604 epistemic violence as much as possible. Replication, I would argue, is in fact only an
605 indicator of good scientific practice if it respects, and *de facto* supports, these normative
606 commitments; the challenge is thus not only to heed awareness for the importance of

607 reproducibility and replicability in lithic science (e.g., Marwick, 2017, 2025; Farahani, 2024;
608 Riede *et al.*, 2024), but also, crucially, to mobilize these calls in such a way that practical
609 implementations actually serve the values of science.

610 As a last point, I want to briefly draw attention to epistemic courage as a related virtue
611 of science that should not be overlooked in the context of ensuing debates on reproducibility
612 and replicability in lithic studies and beyond. Epistemic courage cannot only be associated
613 with resisting the temptations of majority positions and remaining responsive, as well as
614 openly augmenting, marginal voices if needed, it can also be understood as the willingness to
615 take epistemic risks even when the outcome cannot be gauged yet. This normative
616 commitment to pushing into the unknown and unconceived before there is broader agreement
617 that such explorations are worthwhile is relevant for discussing replication in lithic studies
618 because the way replication is commonly understood there often appears to aim at the
619 *reduction* of epistemic risk: attempts to improve the inter-observer reliability of lithic
620 observations (e.g., Pargeter *et al.*, 2023; Kot *et al.*, 2025) are easily read as recommendations
621 of which observations to rely on and which not, even though the respective data can also be
622 interpreted as a measure for the relative risk of *making* particular observations. Some
623 observations are more difficult to make than others, too, but just like riskier observation, as
624 long as we do not know the relative *returns* of such observation – i.e., what they allow us to
625 learn about lithic technology and thereby advance different knowledge-making projects – we
626 should not dismiss them only because they initially appear to be less reproducible than others,
627 notably when there is reason to suspect that this has less to do with the observation itself than
628 with the observational capacity and literacy of the subject lithic analysts.

629

630 **Figure 2.** Revised model of the core values of OS implementation and their ‘direction of travel’
631 (redrawn from Leonelli, 2023: Fig. 2).

632 Taken together, all of these considerations indicate that the rhetorics of replication
633 must also be assessed in relation to their ability to respond to, and ally themselves with,
634 urgent normative concerns within the enterprise we call science. The arguments raised, and
635 the concerns brought forward, indeed suggest, following Leonelli’s (2023) seminal proposal
636 for OS in general, that it would be prudent to invert how openness is conceptualized in lithic
637 studies and thus to rethink how it can best be secured (**Fig. 2**). The resulting inverted
638 ‘direction of travel’ of implementing OS core values results in the prioritization of parameters
639 of *inclusion* rather than of *transparency* as in the traditional scheme. Standards of replication,
640 I argue, must abide to this architecture and respond to its core exigencies.

641

642 **Conclusions**

643 Deep-time lithic studies have been pivoted as yet another arena of the replication crisis, said
644 to increasingly engulf the sciences as a whole. This paper has considered the main thrust of,
645 and the arguments brought forward by, new research in the field aiming to improve the
646 reproducibility of lithic data and the replicability of lithic results, and thus to (finally) place
647 lithic studies on a proper ‘scientific’ footing. I have suggested that the trust in a particular
648 vision of science on which such proposals are typically based is largely unfounded, often
649 risks portraying science in anachronistic terms, and even plays into the hands of those who

650 wittingly or unwittingly lean towards attitudes of science triumphalism and scientism –
651 attitudes that ultimately threaten to undermine the integrity of science. I have offered another
652 vision of the scientific conduct – in-the-making in the philosophy of science and broader
653 science studies for more than three decades now – forwarding an alternative set of criteria for
654 what can reasonably count as scientific and why, placing emphasis in particular on a diversity
655 of open, self-correcting expert communities and their evolved means to assess, critique, and
656 corroborate observations adapted to specific knowledge-making projects. I have argued that
657 calls for replication in lithic studies and archaeology more broadly need to take careful stock
658 of these changed conditions of negotiating scientificity, as they require us to rethink the scope
659 and remit of particular notions of replication and raise issues of epistemic diversity, humility,
660 justice, and courage, and, if not carefully considered, feed the rhetorics of those who
661 wittingly or unwittingly seek to revert back to outdated processualist ideals.

662

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669

670 **Competing Interests**

671 The author declares no competing interests.

672

673

674 **References**

- 675 Araujo, A.G. de M. and Okumura, M. (2021) ‘Cultural Taxonomies in Eastern South
676 America: Historical Review and Perspectives’, *Journal of Paleolithic Archaeology*, 4(4), p.
677 28. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-021-00101-9>.
- 678 Baker, M. (2016) ‘1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility’, *Nature*, 533(7604), pp. 452–
679 454. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/533452a>.
- 680 Barton, C.M. and Clark, G.A. (2021) ‘From Artifacts to Cultures: Technology, Society, and
681 Knowledge in the Upper Paleolithic’, *Journal of Paleolithic Archaeology*, 4(2), p. 16.
682 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-021-00091-8>.
- 683 Bar-Yosef, O. and Van Peer, P. (2009) ‘The Chaîne Opératoire Approach in Middle
684 Paleolithic Archaeology’, *Current Anthropology*, 50(1), pp. 103–131. Available at:
685 <https://doi.org/10.1086/592234>.
- 686 Bates, C. (1997) ‘Climate of mistrust’, *Nature*, 385(6614), pp. 290–290. Available at:
687 <https://doi.org/10.1038/385290c0>.
- 688 Benhabib, S. (2002) *The claims of culture: equality and diversity in the global era*. Princeton,
689 N.J: Princeton University Press.
- 690 Binford, L.R. (2016) *Debating archaeology*. Updated paperback edition. Abingdon, Oxon:
691 Routledge.
- 692 Boëda, E. (2013) *Techno-logique & technologie: une paléo-histoire des objets lithiques*
693 *tranchants*. Prigonrieux: @RChéo-éditions.com.
- 694 Boëda, É. *et al.* (2015) ‘Un débitage lamellaire au Proche-Orient vers 40 000anscal BP. Le
695 site d’Umm el Tlel, Syrie centrale’, *L’Anthropologie*, 119(2), pp. 141–169. Available at:
696 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anthro.2015.04.001>.
- 697 Boëda, E. and Bonilauri, S. (2006) ‘The Intermediate Paleolithic: The First Bladelet
698 Production 40,000 Years Ago’, *Anthropologie (1962-)*, 44(1), pp. 75–92.
- 699 Boëda, É. and Chazan, M. (2023) *Techno-logic and technology: a Paleo-history of Knapped*
700 *Lithic objects*. London: Routledge.
- 701 Carmignani, L. *et al.* (2024) ‘IUP Technological Signatures or Mousterian Variability? The
702 Case of Riparo l’Oscurusciuto (Southern Italy)’, *Journal of Paleolithic Archaeology*, 7(1), p.
703 31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-024-00196-w>.
- 704 Cartwright, N. *et al.* (2022) *The tangle of science: reliability beyond method, rigour, and*
705 *objectivity*. First edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- 706 Chang, H. (2012) *Is Water H2O?: Evidence, Realism and Pluralism*. Dordrecht: Springer
707 Netherlands (Boston Studies in the Philosophy and History of Science). Available at:
708 <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-3932-1>.

709 Chazan, M. (1997) ‘Redefining Levallois’, *Journal of Human Evolution*, 33(6), pp. 719–735.
710 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1006/jhev.1997.0167>.

711 Clark, G.A. (2003) ‘American Archaeology’s Uncertain Future’, *Archeological Papers of the*
712 *American Anthropological Association*, 13(1), pp. 51–67.

713 Clark, G.A. and Riel-Salvatore, J. (2006) ‘Observations on Systematics in Paleolithic
714 Archaeology’, in E. Hovers and S.L. Kuhn (eds) *Transitions Before the Transition: Evolution*
715 *and Stability in the Middle Paleolithic and Middle Stone Age*. Boston, MA: Springer US, pp.
716 29–56. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-24661-4_3.

717 Corbey, R. (2005) *The metaphysics of apes: negotiating the animal-human boundary*.
718 Cambridge ; New York: Cambridge University Press.

719 Daston, L. and Galison, P. (2010) *Objectivity*. 1. paperback ed. New York: Zone Books.

720 Daston, L. and Lunbeck, E. (eds) (2011) *Histories of scientific observation*. Chicago ;
721 London: The University of Chicago Press.

722 Delpiano, D. *et al.* (2024) ‘Not just a technique! An experimental approach to refine the
723 definition of the bipolar anvil reduction in the Uluzzian’, *Archaeological and*
724 *Anthropological Sciences*, 16(12), p. 202. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-024-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-024-02097-z)
725 [02097-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-024-02097-z).

726 Dupré, J. (1993) *The disorder of things: metaphysical foundations of the disunity of science*.
727 Cambridge (Mass.): Harvard University Press.

728 Earle, T.K. *et al.* (1987) ‘Processual Archaeology and the Radical Critique [and Comments
729 and Reply]’, *Current Anthropology*, 28(4), pp. 501–538.

730 Eberl, M. *et al.* (2023) ‘Machine Learning–Based Identification of Lithic Microdebitage’,
731 *Advances in Archaeological Practice*, 11(2), pp. 152–163. Available at:
732 <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2022.35>.

733 Faivre, J.-P. (2012) ‘A Material Anecdote But Technical Reality’, *Lithic Technology*, 37(1),
734 pp. 5–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1179/lit.2012.37.1.5>.

735 Farahani, A. (2024) ‘Reproducibility and Archaeological Practice in the Journal of Field
736 Archaeology’, *Journal of Field Archaeology*, 49(6), pp. 391–394. Available at:
737 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00934690.2024.2391623>.

738 Frank, A., Gleiser, M. and Thompson, E. (2024) *The blind spot: why science cannot ignore*
739 *human experience*. Cambridge, Massachusetts London, England: The MIT Press.

740 Fricker, M. (2007) *Epistemic injustice: power and the ethics of knowing*. Oxford: Oxford
741 University Press.

742 Galison, P. (1997) *Image and logic: a material culture of microphysics*. Chicago: University
743 of Chicago Press.

- 744 Galison, P.L. and Stump, D.J. (1996) *The Disunity of Science: Boundaries, Contexts, and*
745 *Power*. Stanford University Press.
- 746 Gennai, J. (2021) ‘Set in Stone? Discussing the early Upper Palaeolithic taxonomy using
747 European and Levantine assemblages’, *Materiale și Cercetări Arheologice*, (S1), pp. 183–
748 216.
- 749 González-Ruibal, A., Hernando, A. and Politis, G. (2011) ‘Ontology of the self and material
750 culture: Arrow-making among the Awá hunter–gatherers (Brazil)’, *Journal of*
751 *Anthropological Archaeology*, 30(1), pp. 1–16. Available at:
752 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2010.10.001>.
- 753 Haack, S. (2007) *Defending science - within reason: between scientism and cynicism*.
754 Paperback ed. Amherst, NY: Prometheus Books.
- 755 Haack, S. (2012) ‘Six Signs of Scientism’, *Logos & Episteme*, 3(1), pp. 75–95. Available at:
756 <https://doi.org/10.5840/logos-episteme20123151>.
- 757 Hacking, I. (1996) ‘The Disunities of the Sciences’, in *The Disunity of Science*. Stanford:
758 Stanford University Press, pp. 37–74.
- 759 Haraway, D. (1988) ‘Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the
760 Privilege of Partial Perspective’, *Feminist Studies*, 14(3), pp. 575–599. Available at:
761 <https://doi.org/10.2307/3178066>.
- 762 Haraway, D.J. (1991) *Simians, cyborgs, and women: the reinvention of nature*. New York:
763 Routledge.
- 764 Harding, S.G. (1991) *Whose science? Whose knowledge? thinking from women’s lives*. Ithaca,
765 N.Y: Cornell University Press.
- 766 Haufe, C. (2023) *Do the humanities create knowledge?* Cambridge, United Kingdom New
767 York, NY: Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009067508>.
- 768 Hoagland, S.L. (2020) ‘Aspects of the Coloniality of Knowledge’, *Critical Philosophy of*
769 *Race*, 8(1–2), pp. 48–60. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5325/critphilrace.8.1-2.0048>.
- 770 Hussain, S.T. (2019) *The French-Anglophone divide in lithic research: A plea for pluralism in*
771 *Palaeolithic Archaeology*. Leiden: Open Access Leiden Dissertations. Available at:
772 <https://hdl.handle.net/1887/69812>.
- 773 Hussain, S.T. (2021) ‘Compelling image-worlds: a pictorial perspective on the epistemology of
774 stone artefact analysis in Palaeolithic archaeology’, in *New Advances in the History of*
775 *Archaeology*. Oxford: Archaeopress, pp. 138–170.
- 776 Hussain, S.T. (2024) ‘Transformation analysis and systems-theory: from micro-scale lithic
777 technical systems to macro-scale lithic ecosystems’, in *Studying Technology of Non-*
778 *Analogous Environments and Glacial Ecosystems*. Bonn: Habelt, pp. 15–31.

779 Hussain, S.T. (in press) ‘The Loss of Typological Innocence: Pluralism in the Epistemology
780 and Ontology of Archaeological Typo-Praxis’, in *Between variability and singularity:
781 crossing theoretical, qualitative and computer-based approaches to types and typologies in
782 archaeology*. Leiden: Sidestone Press, p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14541419>.

783 Hussain, S.T. and Soressi, M. (2021) ‘The Technological Condition of Human Evolution:
784 Lithic Studies as Basic Science’, *Journal of Paleolithic Archaeology*, 4(3), p. 25. Available at:
785 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-021-00098-1>.

786 Ioannidis, J.P.A. (2005) ‘Why Most Published Research Findings Are False’, *PLOS*
787 *Medicine*, 2(8), p. e124. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0020124>.

788 Kellert, S.H., Longino, H.E. and Waters, C.K. (eds) (2006) *Scientific pluralism*. Minneapolis,
789 MN: University of Minnesota Press (Minnesota studies in the philosophy of science, v. 19).

790 Kitcher, P. (1990) ‘The Division of Cognitive Labor’, *The Journal of Philosophy*, 87(1), pp.
791 5–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2026796>.

792 Kot, M. *et al.* (2025) ‘Reliability and validity in determining the relative chronology between
793 neighbouring scars on flint artefacts’, *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 175, p. 106156.
794 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2025.106156>.

795 Kristiansen, K. (2014) ‘Towards a New Paradigm? The Third Science Revolution and its
796 Possible Consequences in Archaeology’, *Current Swedish Archaeology*, 22(1), pp. 11–34.
797 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.37718/CSA.2014.01>.

798 Kristiansen, K. (2017) ‘The Nature of Archaeological Knowledge and Its Ontological Turns’,
799 *Norwegian Archaeological Review*, 50(2), pp. 120–123. Available at:
800 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00293652.2017.1372802>.

801 Kuhn, T.S. (2020) *Die Struktur wissenschaftlicher Revolutionen*. Zweite revidierte und um
802 das Postskriptum von 1969 ergänzte Auflage, 26. Auflage. Translated by H. Vetter. Frankfurt
803 am Main: Suhrkamp (Suhrkamp-Taschenbuch Wissenschaft, 25).

804 Latour, B. and Woolgar, S. (1986) *Laboratory life: the construction of scientific facts*.
805 Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press.

806 Leonelli, S. (2023) *Philosophy of open science*. Cambridge, United Kingdom New York, NY:
807 Cambridge University Press (Cambridge elements. Elements in the philosophy of science).

808 Lewandowsky, S. and Oberauer, K. (2020) ‘Low replicability can support robust and efficient
809 science’, *Nature Communications*, 11(1), p. 358. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-14203-0)
810 [019-14203-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-14203-0).

811 Longino, H.E. (2020) ‘Science as Social Knowledge : Values and Objectivity in Scientific
812 Inquiry’, pp. 1–280.

813 Lucas, G. (2017) ‘The paradigm concept in archaeology’, *World Archaeology*, 49(2), pp.
814 260–270. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.2016.1252688>.

815 Lucas, G. (2022) ‘Archaeology, Typology and Machine Epistemology’. Available at:
816 <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7620824>.

817 Ludwig, D. and Ruphy, S. (2021) ‘Scientific Pluralism’, in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of*
818 *Philosophy*. Winter 2021 Edition. Stanford: Stanford University Press, p.
819 <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2021/entries/scientific-pluralism/>>.

820 Marwick, B. (2017) ‘Computational Reproducibility in Archaeological Research: Basic
821 Principles and a Case Study of Their Implementation’, *Journal of Archaeological Method*
822 *and Theory*, 24(2), pp. 424–450. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-015-9272-9>.

823 Marwick, B. *et al.* (2017) ‘Open science in archaeology’, *SAA Archaeological Record*, 17(4),
824 pp. 8–14.

825 Marwick, B. (2025) ‘Is archaeology a science? Insights and imperatives from 10,000 articles
826 and a year of reproducibility reviews’, *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 180, p. 106281.
827 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2025.106281>.

828 Massimi, M. (2022) *Perspectival realism*. New York: Oxford University Press (Oxford
829 studies in philos science series).

830 Matzig, D.N., Hussain, S.T. and Riede, F. (2021) ‘Design Space Constraints and the Cultural
831 Taxonomy of European Final Palaeolithic Large Tanged Points: A Comparison of
832 Typological, Landmark-Based and Whole-Outline Geometric Morphometric Approaches’,
833 *Journal of Paleolithic Archaeology*, 4(4), p. 27. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-021-00097-2)
834 [021-00097-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41982-021-00097-2).

835 McElreath, R. and Smaldino, P.E. (2015) ‘Replication, Communication, and the Population
836 Dynamics of Scientific Discovery’, *PLOS ONE*, 10(8), p. e0136088. Available at:
837 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0136088>.

838 Ngugi wa Thiong’o (2011) *Decolonising the mind: the politics of language in African*
839 *literature*. Oxford: Currey [u.a.].

840 Nosek, B.A. *et al.* (2022) ‘Replicability, Robustness, and Reproducibility in Psychological
841 Science’, *Annual Review of Psychology*, 73(Volume 73, 2022), pp. 719–748. Available at:
842 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-020821-114157>.

843 Oreskes, N. (2021) *Why trust science?* Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press
844 (University Center for Human Values series).

845 Pargeter, J. *et al.* (2023) ‘Replicability in Lithic Analysis’, *American Antiquity*, 88(2), pp.
846 163–186. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/aaq.2023.4>.

847 Peels, R. and Bouter, L. (2023) ‘Replication and trustworthiness’, *Accountability in Research*,
848 30(2), pp. 77–87. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2021.1963708>.

849 Pepper, S.C. (1972) *World hypotheses: a study in evidence*. 7. print. Berkeley, Calif.: Univ. of
850 California Pr.

- 851 Pickering, A. (ed.) (1995) *The mangle of practice: time, agency, and science*. Chicago:
852 University of Chicago Press.
- 853 Prentiss, W.C. (1998) ‘The Reliability and Validity of a Lithic Debitage Typology:
854 Implications for Archaeological Interpretation’, *American Antiquity*, 63(4), pp. 635–650.
855 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2694112>.
- 856 Reynolds, N. and Riede, F. (2019) ‘House of cards: cultural taxonomy and the study of the
857 European Upper Palaeolithic’, *Antiquity*, 93(371), pp. 1350–1358. Available at:
858 <https://doi.org/10.15184/aqy.2019.49>.
- 859 Ribeiro, A. (2019) ‘Science, Data, and Case-Studies under the Third Science Revolution:
860 Some Theoretical Considerations’, *Current Swedish Archaeology*, 27(1), pp. 115–132.
861 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.37718/CSA.2019.06>.
- 862 Riede, F. (2017) ‘The “Bromme problem” – notes on understanding the Federmessergruppen
863 and Bromme culture occupation in southern Scandinavia during the Allerød and early
864 Younger Dryas chronozones’, in *Problems in Palaeolithic and Mesolithic Research*, pp. 61–
865 85.
- 866 Riede, F. *et al.* (2020) ‘Cultural taxonomies in the Paleolithic—Old questions, novel
867 perspectives’, *Evolutionary Anthropology*, 29(2), pp. 49–52. Available at:
868 <https://doi.org/10.1002/evan.21819>.
- 869 Riede, F. *et al.* (2024) ‘A quantitative analysis of Final Palaeolithic/earliest Mesolithic
870 cultural taxonomy and evolution in Europe’, *PLOS ONE*, 19(3), p. e0299512. Available at:
871 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0299512>.
- 872 Riede, F., Hoggard, C. and Shennan, S. (2019) ‘Reconciling material cultures in archaeology
873 with genetic data requires robust cultural evolutionary taxonomies’, *Palgrave
874 Communications*, 5(1), pp. 1–9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0260-7>.
- 875 Robinson, D.N. and Williams, R.N. (eds) (2014) *Scientism: the new orthodoxy*. London New
876 York: Bloomsbury Academic.
- 877 Sandgathe, D.M. (2004) ‘Alternative Interpretation of the Levallois Reduction Technique’,
878 *Lithic Technology*, 29(2), pp. 147–159. Available at:
879 <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2004.11721017>.
- 880 Santo, F.D. (2024) ‘Between Understanding and Control: Science as a Cultural Product’,
881 *Foundations of Science* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10699-024-09960-1>.
- 882 Santos, B. de S. (2016) *Epistemologies of the South: justice against epistemicide*. London
883 New York: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315634876>.
- 884 Schurz, G. and Carrier, M. (eds) (2013) *Werte in den Wissenschaften: neue Ansätze zum
885 Werturteilsstreit*. Erste Auflage, Originalausgabe. Berlin: Suhrkamp (Suhrkamp Taschenbuch
886 Wissenschaft, 2062).

- 887 Shepherd, N. (2020) ‘The grammar of decoloniality’, in *Colonial and Decolonial Linguistics: Knowledges and Epistemes*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 303–324.
- 889 Smaldino, P.E. and McElreath, R. (2016) ‘The natural selection of bad science’, *Royal Society Open Science*, 3(9), p. 160384. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.160384>.
- 891 Smith, M.E. *et al.* (2012) ‘Archaeology as a social science’, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(20), pp. 7617–7621. Available at:
892 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1201714109>.
- 894 Soler, L. *et al.* (eds) (2014) *Science after the Practice Turn in the Philosophy, History, and Social Studies of Science*. New York: Routledge. Available at:
895 <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315857985>.
- 897 Sørensen, T.F. (2017) ‘The Two Cultures and a World Apart: Archaeology and Science at a
898 New Crossroads’, *Norwegian Archaeological Review*, 50(2), pp. 101–115. Available at:
899 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00293652.2017.1367031>.
- 900 Staddon, J.E.R. (2018) *Scientific method: how science works, fails to work, and pretends to work*. New York: Routledge.
- 902 Stenmark, M. (2017) *Scientism: Science, Ethics and Religion*. 1st ed. Oxford: Taylor &
903 Francis Group (Routledge Revivals Series).
- 904 Stewart, A.J. and Plotkin, J.B. (2021) ‘The natural selection of good science’, *Nature Human Behaviour*, 5(11), pp. 1510–1518. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01111-x>.
- 906 Stroud, S.R. (2015) ‘Pragmatism, Pluralism, and World Hypotheses: Stephen Pepper and the
907 Metaphysics of Criticism’, *Philosophy & Rhetoric*, 48(3), pp. 266–291. Available at:
908 <https://doi.org/10.5325/philrhet.48.3.0266>.
- 909 Timbrell, L. *et al.* (2022) ‘Testing inter-observer error under a collaborative research
910 framework for studying lithic shape variability’, *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences*, 14(10), p. 209. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-022-01676-2>.
- 912 Torrence, R., Martínón-Torres, M. and Rehren, Th. (2015) ‘Forty years and still growing:
913 *Journal of Archaeological Science* looks to the future’, *Journal of Archaeological Science*,
914 56, pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2015.03.001>.
- 915 Trigger, B.G. (2006) *A history of archaeological thought*. Second edition. Cambridge:
916 Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511813016>.
- 917 Tuck, E. and Yang, K.W. (2012) ‘Decolonization is not a metaphor’, *Decolonization: Indigeneity, Education & Society*, 1(1). Available at:
918 <https://jps.library.utoronto.ca/index.php/des/article/view/18630> (Accessed: 8 August 2025).
- 920 Vaesen, K. and Hussain, S.T. (2025) ‘The Perks and Perils of Replicability’, *American Antiquity*, p. in press.

- 922 Weedman Arthur, K.J. (2017) *The lives of stone tools: crafting the status, skill, and identity of*
923 *flintknappers*. Tucson: The University of Arizona Press.
- 924 Wilkins, J. (2020) ‘Is it Time to Retire NASTIES in Southern African? Moving Beyond the
925 Culture-historical Framework for Middle Stone Age Lithic Assemblage Variability’, *Lithic*
926 *Technology*, 0(0), pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2020.1802848>.
- 927 Will, M. *et al.* (2019) ‘Comparative analysis of Middle Stone Age artifacts in Africa
928 (CoMSAfrica)’, *Evolutionary Anthropology: Issues, News, and Reviews*, 28(2), pp. 57–59.
929 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/evan.21772>.
- 930 Wylie, A. (2015) ‘A Plurality of Pluralisms: Collaborative Practice in Archaeology’, in F.
931 Padovani, A. Richardson, and J.Y. Tsou (eds) *Objectivity in Science: New Perspectives from*
932 *Science and Technology Studies*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Boston Studies in
933 the Philosophy and History of Science), pp. 189–210. Available at:
934 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14349-1_10.
- 935 Zwyns, N. *et al.* (2012) ‘Burin-core technology and laminar reduction sequences in the initial
936 Upper Paleolithic from Kara-Bom (Gorny-Altai, Siberia)’, *Quaternary International*, 259, pp.
937 33–47. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2011.03.036>.
- 938